

**ACUTE TOXICITY AND ANTICONVULSANT ACTIVITY OF
5- (p-AMINOPHENYL) - 4-AMINO-1,2,4-TRIAZOLE-3(2H) -
THIONE**

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1,2,4-triazole-3(2H)-thione,

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ABSTRACT

In this article, it has been experimentally confirmed that 5-(p-aminophenyl)-4-amino-1,2,4-triazole-3(2H)-thione belongs to the class of low-toxic psychopharmacological activity in doses of 0.1; 0.5; 1.0; 5.0 and 10.0 mg/kg and is not inferior to comparable anticonvulsant drugs carbamazepine and convulex.

ОСТРАЯ ТОКСИЧНОСТЬ И ПРОТИВОСУДОРОЖНАЯ АКТИВНОСТЬ 5 - (п-АМИНОФЕНИЛ) - 4-АМИНО-1,2,4-ТРИАЗОЛ-3 (2Н) - ТИОНА

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активность, карбамазепин,

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ABSTRACT

В этой статье экспериментально подтверждено, что 5-(п-аминофенил)-4-амино-1,2,4-триазол-3(2H)-тион относится к классу малотоксичных, по психофармакологической активности в дозах 0,1; 0,5; 1,0; 5,0 и 10,0 мг/кг и не уступает сопоставимым противосудорожным препаратам карбамазепину и конвулексу.

**5-(p-AMINOFENIL)-4-AMINO-1,2,4-TRIAZOL-3(2H)-TIONNING O'TKIR
ZAHARLILIGI VA TUTQANOQQA QARSHI FAOLLIGI**

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5-(p-aminofenil)-4-amino-1,2,4-triazol-3(2H)-tion, kam zaharli, psixofarmakologik faollik, tutqanoqqa qarshi faollik, karbamazepin, konvuleks.

ABSTRACT

Ushbu maqolada 5-(p-aminofenil)-4-amino-1,2,4-triazol-3(2H)-tion kam zaharli sinfga mansub ekanligi, 0.1; 0.5; 1.0; 5.0 va 10.0 mg/kg dozalarda psixofarmakologik faolliklari va tutqanoqqa qarshi solishtirma preparatlar karbamazepin va konvuleksdan qolishmasligi eksperimental tajribalar asosida tasdiqlangan.

Dolzarbli. Epilepsiya – bu markaziy nerv tizimi neyronlarining faoliyatini buzilishi bilan kechadigan surunkali kasallik hisoblanib, bosh miyaning qo'zg'atuvchi va tormozlovchi mediatorlar faoliyatini disbalansi evaziga tutqanoq va es-hushni yoqolishi bilan xarakterlanadi [1, 2]. So'nggi bir necha o'n yilliklar davomida 20 dan ortiq yangi antiepileptik dorilar, shu jumladan eslikarbazepin asetat [3], perampanel [4] va ezogabin [5] yaratilgan. Biroq, aholining katta qismi monoterapiya [6] bilan turg'un antikonvulsant samaraga erisha olmaydi va bemorlarning taxminan 30% refrakter epilepsiyaga ega va davolash kombinatsiyasini talab qiladi [7, 8]. Bundan tashqari, ko'plab antiepileptik dori preparatlarning jiddiy nojo'ya ta'siri mavjud [9, 10] va umrbod davolanish kerak. Shuning uchun ko'proq tanlangan va xavfsizroq antikonvulsant vositalarni izlash alohida qiziqish uyg'otadi. Shu nuqtai nazardan, turli yondashuvlar bir necha antiepileptik dori [11-13] rivojlantirish uchun o'rganildi.

Asosiy ingibirlovchi neyromediator bo'lgan γ -Amino moy kislotasi (GAMK) ning rivojlanishi neyrodegenerativ kasalliklar sohasidagi faol tadqiqot sohasidir. GAMK-A retseptorlari barbituratlar, steroidlar, anestetiklar va benzodiazepinlar kabi bir qator terapevtik muhim dorilar uchun [14,15] asosiy nishon hisoblanadi. 1,2,4-triazol hosilalari ko'plab biologik faolliklarni, jumladan, antikonvulsant [16, 17], zamburug'ga qarshi [18-20], neyrotrop geterosiklik faollik [21-24], yallig'lanishga qarshi [25-27] va antibakterial [28-31], namoyon qilishi tajribalarda asoslantirilgan. Savdoda mavjud bo'lgan antiepileptik dorilarning molekulyar tuzilishi va bioaktivligi fazoviy uzoq gidrofob domenlar (odatda fenil halqalari), vodorod bilan bog'lanish domenlari va elektron donorlik fragmentlari, bu yuqori antikonvulsant faollik uchun zarur bo'lgan elementlardir. Boshqa tomondan, qanot va uning hamkasblari loreklezolning (ikkinchi avlod antiepileptik dori) faolligi triazol qismining asparagin amid guruhi (Asn-289) GABA-A retseptorlari 2 subbirliklari bilan o'zaro ta'siriga bog'liqligini taklif qilishdi. Bundan tashqari, 1,2,4-triazol qismiga ega bo'lgan turli xil boshqa

birikmalar epilepsiyaning bir nechta hayvon modellarida antikonvulsant xususiyatlarga ega ekanligi aniqlandi [32-35]. Ushbu topilmalar bizni antikonvulsant faollik bilan ta'minlangan 1,2,4-triazol asosidagi birikmalarni izlashga va olingan hosilalarning GABA-A retseptorlarining allosterik joyida harakat qilishi mumkinligini aniqlashga undadi. Ushbu tadqiqotda biz *in vivo* eksperimental modellar yordamida potentsial antikonvulsant modda sifatida 5-(p-aminofenil)-4-amino-1,2,4-triazol-3(2H)-tionning shartli ravishda (D-280) yangi sintez qilingan birikmani, farmakologik baholash bo'yicha tadqiqotlar o'tkazildi.

Tadqiqot maqsadi. 5-(p-aminofenil)-4-amino-1,2,4-triazol-3(2H)-tionning o'tkir zaharliligi, harakat faolligiga ta'siri, "ochiq maydon" usulida harakat va qidiruv faolligiga ta'siri va tutqanoqqa qarshi faolliklarini eksperimental baholashdan iborat.

Tadqiqot material va usullari: Tadqiqotlar O'zRFA O'simlik moddalari kimyosi instituti farmakologiya va toksikologiya bo'limi vivariy sharoitida 14 kun davomida karantinda saqlangan tana massasi 17-24 g. bo'lgan oq sichqonlarda olib borildi. Tajribalar xona harorati 20-25°C, havo nisbiy namligi 35-40%, yoritish darajasi 400 lyuks bo'lgan sharoitda olib borildi. Tajribalar institutning Organik sintez bo'limi xodimlari D.S. Ismailova va B.J. Elmuradovlar tomonidan sintezlangan 5-(p-aminofenil)-4-amino-1,2,4-triazol-3(2H)-tionning 0.1; 0.5; 1.0; 5.0 va 10 mg/kg dozada hamda solishtirma preparatlarda har bir guruhda 8 tadan oq sichqonlarda yuqoridagi faolliklari bo'yicha baholab chiqildi. Tajribalarda D-280 birikmasi 60 daqiqa oldin yuborilib, keyin tutqanoq chaqiradigan analizatorlar yuborilgan. Tadqiqotlar uchun pentilentetrazol, strixninlar Sigma-Aldrich® kompaniyasi maxsulotlari foydalanildi. Birikma suvda erimaganligi sababli, og'iz orqali yuborilganda TVIN-80 moddasida eritilib, 100 mg/kg dozadan 9000 mg/kg dozagacha sinovdan 14 kun davomida o'tkazildi. O'tkir zaharlilik bo'yicha olingan natijalar asosida Kerber usulida hisoblandi. Olingan natijalar statistik tahlili R.B. Strelkov taklif qilgan usullar yordamida ($p \leq 0.05$) tahlil qilindi.

Olingan natijalar. 5-(p-aminofenil)-4-amino-1,2,4-triazol-3(2H)-tionning o'tkir zaharliligi dastlab 100-500 mg/kg dozada og'iz orqali yuborilganda hech qanday patologik o'zgarishlar kuzatilmadi. 500-1500 mg/kg dozada esa qisqa muddatda nafas tezlashganligi kuzatildi. 2000 mg/kg dozadan boshlab, umumiy holsizlik va harakat faolligida cheklanishlar kuzatila boshlandi. 4000-9000 mg/kg dozada esa 3-12 soat oralig'ida tremor, tutqanoq holatlari yuzaga kelib, o'lim qayd etildi. O'rtacha o'lim dozasi $LD_{50} = 4400$ mg/kg tashkil etdi.

5-(p-aminofenil)-4-amino-1,2,4-triazol-3(2H)-tionning 0.1; 0.5; 1.0; 5.0 va 10 mg/kg dozada og'iz orqali yuborilib, 60 daqiqadan so'ng harakat faolligi (HF) va vertikalizatsiya ko'rsatkichlari baholandi. 0.1 va 10 mg/kg dozalarda harakat faolligini kamaytirib, 0.5; 1.0 va 5.0 mg/kg dozalarda HF oshirganligini, vertikalizatsiya bo'yicha esa 0.1; 0.5; 1.0 va 5.0 mg/kg dozada nazorat guruhiga nisbatan yuqori faollik namoyon etgan. Olingan natijalar 1-rasmda ko'rsatilgan.

1-rasm. D-280 birikmasini turli dozalarda oq sichqonlarda bir marotaba yuborilganda harakat faolligiga ta'siri

D-280 birikmasini "ochiq maydon" usulida harakat va qidiruv faolligiga ta'sirini baholash. 5-(p-aminofenil)-4-amino-1,2,4-triazol-3(2H)-tionning 0.1; 0.5; 1.0; 5.0 va 10 mg/kg dozada og'iz orqali yuborilib, 60 daqiqadan so'ng harakat faoligi kvadratlar kesishmasidagi o'tishlar soniga qarab va qidiruv faoligi esa tuynuklardan mo'ralashiga qarab baho beriladi. Olingan natijalar 1-jadvalda ko'rsatilgan.

1-jadval. D-280 birikmasini "ochiq maydon" usulida harakat va qidiruv faolligiga ta'sirini baholash

Dozalar mg/kg	Nazorat guruhi	0.1	0.5	1.0	5.0	10.0
Ko'rsatkishlar						
Harakat faolligi	12.2±1.24	13.4±0.93*	14.2±0.62*	15.4±2.17*	14.8±1.24*	15.2±0.93*
Qidiruv faolligi	10.0±0.62	13.8±1.24*	15.2±2.17*	16.8±1.24*	15.8±0.93*	16.4±2.17*

Eslatma. $P < 0.05$ nazorat guruhiga nisbatan

Olingan natijalarga asoslanib, D-280 birikmasi barcha dozalarda harakat va qidiruv faolligini oshirganligini ko'rishimiz mumkin.

D-280 birikmasini turli dozalarda strixnin ta'sirida chaqirilgan tutqanoqqa qarshi ta'sirini o'rganish. Bu test odamlarda birlamchi-tarqalgan tutqanoqqa o'xshash holatlarni yuzaga chiqaradi. Ushbu modeldagi birikmalarning antikonsulsant faoligi gliksinga sezgir retseptorlarning bevosita faollashishi va gliksin va GAMK-ergik faollikning birgalikda kuchayishi bilan bog'liq bo'lishi mumkin. Strixnin yuborilgandan so'ng, nazorat hayvonlarining 100% tonik-klonik tutqanoqlar rivojlandi. Tajribalar oq sichqonlarda 1.5 mg/kg strixnin teri ostiga yuborib o'rganildi. O'rganiluvchi modda 0.1; 0.5; 1.0; 5.0 va 10 mg/kg dozada og'iz orqali yuborilganda tutqanoqning latent davrini nazorat va solishtirma preparatga yaqin ta'sir etganligi, tutqanoqlar sonini oshirganligi hamda o'lim yuzaga kelish vaqti bo'yicha deyarli bir xil faollik namoyon qildi. Olingan natijalar 2-jadvalda ko'rsatilgan.

2-jadval. D-280 birikmasini strixnin yordamida chaqirilgan tutqanoqqa ta'sirini baholash (n=8)

O'rganilgan modda	Doza, mg/kg	Tutqanoq boshlanish vaqti (daqiqa)	Tutqanoqlar soni	O'lim vaqti (daqiqa)	O'lgan soni
Nazorat (strixnin t/o)	1.5	7.00±0.00	1.00±0.00	7.00±0.00	8
D-280	10.0	5.75±0.62*	1.00±0.00	6.50±0.31	8
	5.0	6.75±1.55	1.25±0.31*	7.25±1.24*	8
	1.0	5.25±0.62*	3.50±1.24*	7.00±2.17	8
	0.5	7.00±0.93	1.25±0.31*	7.75±0.93*	8
	0.1	5.75±0.31*	2.75±0.93*	7.50±0.93*	8
Konvuleks	200.0	7.25±1.24	1.00±0.00	8.25±0.31*	8
	100.0	6.00±0.62	1.25±0.31	6.25±0.31	8
	50.0	7.00±1.24	1.25±0.31	7.00±1.24	8
Karbamazepin	20.0	8.00±0.31*	1.25±0.31*	9.25±0.93*	7*
	50.0	7.00±0.62	1.00±0.00*	7.00±1.24	7*

Eslatma.*P≤0.05 nazorat guruhiga nisbatan

Shunday qilib, sintetik birikma tutqanoq ko'rsatkichlari bo'yicha: tutqanoqlarning boshlanishi, soni va hayvonlarning yashovchanligi bo'yicha nazorat guruhiga hamda Karbamazepin va Konvuleksga yaqin faollik namoyon qilganligi kuzatildi. Sintetik birikma bilan davolangan hayvonlarda strixninni teri ostiga yuborish natijasida kelib chiqadigan tutqanoqlarning yashirin davri davomiyligining statistik jihatdan ahamiyatli o'zgarishligi o'rganilayotgan birikmaning glitsinergik sistemaga ta'sir ko'rsatishini bildiradi.

D-280 birikmasini pentilentetrazol (korazol) ta'sirida chaqirilgan tutqanoqqa qarshi ta'sirini o'rganish.

Ushbu test epilepsiyaga qarshi faolligi mavjud birikmalarning klinik oldi sinovlarini o'tkazish uchun eng zarur usullardan biri hisoblanadi. Pentilentetrazol GAMKA antagonisti hisoblanib, qorin bo'shlig'iga yuborilganda katta (*grand mal*) va kichik (*petit mal*) tutqanoq xurujlarini keltirib chiqarsa, teri ostiga yuborilganda esa kichik tutqanoq xurujlarini "*petit mal*" hamda tutqanoqning asosiy komponenti klonik tutqanoqlarni yuzaga keltiradi. Bosh miya yarim sharlarining harakat zonasini qo'zg'alishi tufayli tutqanoqni yuzaga keltiradigan pentilentetrazol 90 mg/kg dozada teri ostiga yuborildi hamda o'rganiluvchi modda 0.1; 0.5; 1.0; 5.0 va 10 mg/kg dozada og'iz orqali yuborib o'rganildi. Ushbu testda nazorat guruhiga nisbatan latent davrni 1,5-3.0 barobar uzaytirganligi va o'lim yuzaga kelishini kamaytirganligini ko'rish mumkin (3-jadval).

3-jadval. D-280 birikmasini pentilentetrazol yordamida chaqirilgan tutqanoqqa ta'sirini baholash (n=8)

O'rganilgan modda	Doza, mg/kg	Tutqanoq boshlanish vaqti (daqiqa)	Tutqanoqlar soni	O'lim vaqti (daqiqa)	O'lgan soni
Nazorat (pentilentetrazol t/o)	90.0	4.75±0.93	7.00±2.17	15.75±2.79	8
	10.0	13.25±3.41*	5.00±1.86*	25.50±2.79*	6

D-280	5.0	13.00±0.93*	5.00±0.93*	40.00±4.96*	8
	1.0	12.25±4.34*	2.00±0.62*	26.00±11.16*	8
	0.5	10.00±5.58*	4.25±1.24*	24.00±6.20*	6*
	0.1	15.50±1.24*	3.50±0.62*	24.25±7.13*	8
Karbamazepin	20.0	2.70±0.93	2.75±0.31*	5.50±1.24*	8
	50.0	3.05±1.24	2.50±0.62*	9.75±2.79*	8
Konvuleks	100.0	4.60±0.93	5.20±1.24*	12.75±5.20*	7*
	200.0	5.00±0.93*	3.40±1.24*	12.20±2.79*	8

Eslatma.*P≤0.05 nazorat guruhiga nisbatan

Shunday qilib, D-280 birikmasi GAMK_A antagonisti hisoblangan pentilentetrazolga qarshi faolligini inobatga olsak, birikmalar yuqori darajada GAMK_A retseptorlari faolligini oshirganligini ko'rishimiz mumkin. Solishtirma preparatlardan qolishmasligini amalda namoyon etganligini ko'rishimiz mumkin.

Xulosa. D-280 birikmasining o'tkir zaharliligi Stefanov tasnifi bo'yicha IV sinf kam zaharli birikmalar qatoriga kiradi. Harakatlanish aktivligi va "ochiq maydon" usulida harakat va qidiruv faolligini oshirganligini ko'rishimiz mumkin. Pentilentetrazol yordamida chaqirilgan tutqanoqlarda tutqanoq yashirin davrini uzayishiga, yashash davomiyligini oshishiga va o'limlar sonini kamayishiga olib keldi. Tutqanoqqa qarshi faolligi bo'yicha tibbiyot amaliyotida keng qo'llaniladigan preparatlar karbamazepin va konvuleksdan qolishmasligi hatto ba'zi holatlarda ulardan ustunligini tajribalar ko'rsatdi. Ushbu natijalarga asoslanib, tutqanoq yuzaga kelishida muhim o'rin tutadigan glitsinergik va GAMK_A retseptorlari sistemasiga yetarli darajada ta'sir ko'rsatganligini ko'rishimiz mumkin.

References:

1. Strine TW, Kobau R, Chapman DP, Thurman DJ, Price P, Balluz LS. Psychological distress comorbidities and health behaviors among U.S. adults with seizures: results from the 2002 National Health Interview Survey. *Epilepsia*. 2005 Jul;46(7):1133-9. doi:10.1111/j.1528-1167.2005.01605.x, PMID 16026567.
2. Ashhar MU, Ahmad MZ, Jain V, Agarwal NB, Ahmad FJ, Jain GK. Intranasal pitavastatin attenuates seizures in different experimental models of epilepsy in mice. *Epilepsy Behav*. 2017 Oct 1;75:56-9. doi: 10.1016/j.yebeh.2017.07.004, PMID 28826009.
3. Soares DA Silva P, Pires N, Bonifacio MJ, Loureiro AI, Palma N, Wright LC. Eslicarbazepine acetate for the treatment of focal epilepsy: an update on its proposed mechanisms of action. *Pharmacol Res Perspect*. 2015 Mar;3(2):e00124. Doi:10.1002/prp2.124, PMID 26038700
4. Hanada T. The discovery and development of perampanel for the treatment of epilepsy. *Expert Opin Drug Discov*. 2014 Apr 1;9(4):449-58. doi: 10.1517/17460441.2014.891580, PMID 24559052.
5. Large CH, Sokal DM, Nehlig A, Gunthorpe MJ, Sankar R, Crean CS. The spectrum of anticonvulsant efficacy of retigabine (ezogabine) in animal models: implications for clinical use. *Epilepsia*. 2012 Mar;53(3):425-36. doi: 10.1111/j.1528-1167.2011.03364.x, PMID 22221318.

6. Kamboj VK, Verma PK, Dhanda A, Ranjan S. 1,2,4-triazole derivatives as a potential scaffold for anticonvulsant activity. *Cent Nerv Syst Agents Med Chem*. 2015 Apr 1;15(1):17-22. doi: 10.2174/1871524915666150209100533, PMID 25675400.
7. Ben Menachem E. Medical management of refractory epilepsy practical treatment with novel antiepileptic drugs. *Epilepsia*. 2014 Jan;55 Suppl 1:3-8. doi: 10.1111/epi.12494, PMID 24400690.
8. Luszczki JJ, Plech T, Wujec M. Effect of 4-(4-bromophenyl)-5-(3-chlorophenyl)-2,4-dihydro-3H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thione on the anticonvulsant action of different classical antiepileptic drugs in the mouse maximal electroshock induced seizure model. *Eur J Pharmacol*. 2012 Sep 5;690(1-3):99-106. doi: 10.1016/j.ejphar.2012.06.023, PMID 22732650.
9. Loring DW, Meador KJ. Cognitive side effects of antiepileptic drugs in children. *Neurology*. 2004 Mar 23;62(6):872-7. doi: 10.1212/01.wnl.0000115653.82763.07, PMID 15037684.
10. Chen B, Choi H, Hirsch LJ, Katz A, Legge A, Buchsbaum R. Psychiatric and behavioral side effects of antiepileptic drugs in adults with epilepsy. *Epilepsy Behav*. 2017 Nov 1;76:24-31. doi: 10.1016/j.yebeh.2017.08.039, PMID 28931473.
11. Deka D, Chakravarty PI, Purkayastha AY. Evaluation of the anticonvulsant effect of aqueous extract of *Centella asiatica* in albino mice. *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci*. 2017;9(2):312-4. doi: 10.22159/ijpps.2017v9i2.15483.
12. Karakucuk Iyidogan A, Basaran E, Tatar Yilmaz G, Oruc Emre EE. Development of new chiral 1,2,4-triazole-3-thiones and 1,3,4-thiadiazoles with promising *in vivo* anticonvulsant activity targeting GABAergic system and voltage-gated sodium channels (VGSCs). *Bioorg Chem*. 2024 Oct 1;151:107662. doi:10.1016/j.bioorg.2024.107662, PMID 39079390.
13. Rani S, Teotia S, Nain S. Recent advancements and biological activities of triazole derivatives: a short review. *Pharm Chem J*. 2024 Apr 15;57(12):1909-17. doi: 10.1007/s11094-024-03096-z.
14. Mula M. GABAergic drugs in the treatment of epilepsy: modern or outmoded? *Future Med Chem*. 2011 Feb;3(2):177-82. doi: 10.4155/fmc.10.296, PMID 21428812.
15. Froestl W. An historical perspective on GABAergic drugs. *Future Med Chem*. 2011 Feb;3(2):163-75. doi: 10.4155/fmc.10.285, PMID 21428811.
16. Plech T, Luszczki JJ, Wujec M, Flieger J, Pizon M. Synthesis characterization and preliminary anticonvulsant evaluation of some 4-alkyl-1,2,4-triazoles. *Eur J Med Chem*. 2013 Feb 1;60:208-15. doi: 10.1016/j.ejmech.2012.11.026, PMID 23291122.
17. Sanoev Z.I., Ismailova D.S., Rakhimboev S.D., Tolibovich T.T., Elmuradov B.J., Abdinazarov I.T., Rashidov S.Z. (2023). Synthesis And Research Anticonvulsant Activity Of Annulated Triazolo-thiadiazine Derivative In Laboratory Animals. *Biomedical & Pharmacology Journal*. Vol. 16(4), p. 2457-2467.
18. Matin MM, Matin P, Rahman MR, Ben Hadda T, Almalki FA, Mahmud S. Triazoles and their derivatives: chemistry synthesis and therapeutic applications. *Front Mol Biosci*. 2022 Apr 25;9:864286. doi: 10.3389/fmolb.2022.864286, PMID 35547394, PMCID PMC9081720.
19. Zhang Y, Wang M, Ahmed M, HE L, Ji M, Qi Z. Synthesis fungicidal activity and SAR of 3,4-dichloro-isothiazole based cycloalkyl sulfonamides. *Bioorg Med Chem Lett*. 2019 Jun 1;29(11):1345-9. doi: 10.1016/j.bmcl.2019.03.047, PMID 30956010.

20. Zhang Y, Wang M, Ahmed M, He L, Ji M, Qi Z. Synthesis fungicidal activity and SAR of 3,4-dichloroisothiazolebased cycloalkylsulfonamides. *Bioorg Med Chem Lett*. 2019;29(11):1345-49. doi: 10.1016/j.bmcl.2019.03.047, PMID 30956010.
21. Султонов, С. А. У., & Саноев, З. И. (2024). Оценка нейротропной активности синтетических гетероциклических соединений (обзор литературы). *Re-health journal*, (4 (24)), 33-38.
22. Sanoev, Z. I., & Mirzaev, Y. R. (2020). Pharmacological activity of the possessing new atypical neuroleptics 1-phenyltetrahydroisoquinoline structure. *The American Journal of Medical Sciences and Pharmaceutical Research*, 18-26.
23. Sanoev, Z. I., & Mirzaev, Y. R. (2021). Research of a New Atypical Neuroleptic 1-(3', 4'-Methylenedioxyphenyl)-6, 7-Methylenedioxy-1, 2, 3, 4-Tetrahydroisoquinoline on the Central Nervous System. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 25(2), 2363-2369.
24. Turan Zitouni G, Sivaci M, Kilic FS, Erol K. Synthesis of some triazolyl-antipyrine derivatives and investigation of analgesic activity. *Eur J Med Chem*. 2001 Aug 1;36(7-8):685-9. doi:10.1016/s0223-5234(01)01252-1, PMID 11600237.
25. Bekircan O, Kuxuk M, Kahveci B, Kolayli S. Convenient synthesis of fused heterocyclic 1,3,5-triazines from some N-acyl imidates and heterocyclic amines as anticancer and antioxidant agents. *Arch Pharm Int*. 2005 Aug;338(8):365-72. doi: 10.1002/ardp.200400964, PMID 16041836.
26. Wade PC, Vogt BR, Kissick TP, Simpkins LM, Palmer DM, Millonig RC. 1-Acyltriazoles as antiinflammatory agents. *J Med Chem*. 1982 Mar;25(3):331-3. doi: 10.1021/jm00345a021, PMID 6461764.
27. Mahdavi M, Akbarzadeh T, Sheibani V, Abbasi M, Firoozpour L, Tabatabai SA. Synthesis of two novel 3-amino-5-[4-chloro-2- phenoxyphenyl]-4H-1,2,4-triazoles with anticonvulsant activity. *Iran J Pharm Res*. 2010;9(3):265-9. PMID 24363736.
28. Modzelewska Banachiewicz B, Kalabun J. Synthesis and biological action of 5-oxo-1,2,4-triazine derivatives. *Pharmazie*. 1999 Jul 1;54(7):503-5. PMID 10445245.
29. Gupta D, Jain DK. Synthesis antifungal and antibacterial activity of novel 1,2,4-triazole derivatives. *J Adv Pharm Technol Res*. 2015 Jul 1;6(3):141-6. doi: 10.4103/2231-4040.161515, PMID 26317080.
30. Gao F, Wang T, Xiao J, Huang G. Antibacterial activity study of 1,2,4-triazole derivatives. *Eur J Med Chem*. 2019 Jul 1;173:274- 81. doi: 10.1016/j.ejmech.2019.04.043, PMID 31009913.
31. Gulerman N, Rollas S, Kiraz M, Ekinci AC, Vidin A. Evaluation of antimycobacterial and anticonvulsant activities of new 1-(4-fluorobenzoyl)-4-substituted thiosemicarbazide and 5-(4-fluorophenyl)-4-substituted-2,4-dihydro-3H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thione derivatives. *Farmaco*. 1997 Nov 1;52(11):691-5. PMID9550096.
32. Ikizler AA, Johansson CB, Bekircan O, Celik C. Drug synthesis. *Acta Poloniae Pharmaceutica-Drug Research*. 1999;56(4):283-8.
33. Shalini M, Yogeeswari P, Sriram D, Stables JP. Cyclization of the semicarbazone template of aryl semicarbazones: synthesis and anticonvulsant activity of 4,5-diphenyl-2H-1,2,4-triazol-3(4H) one. *Biomed Pharmacother*. 2009 Mar 1;63(3):187-93. doi:10.1016/j.biopha.2006.04.002, PMID 19422088.

34. Siddiqui N, Ahsan W. Triazole incorporated thiazoles as a new class of anticonvulsants: design, synthesis and *in vivo* screening. Eur J Med Chem. 2010 Apr 1;45(4):1536-43. doi: 10.1016/j.ejmech.2009.12.062, PMID 20116140.
35. Almasirad A, Tabatabai SA, Faizi M, Kebriaeezadeh A, Mehrabi N, Dalvandi A. Synthesis and anticonvulsant activity of new 2-substituted-5- [2-(2-fluorophenoxy)phenyl]-1,3,4-oxadiazoles and 1,2,4-triazoles. Bioorg Med Chem Lett. 2004 Dec 20;14(24):6057-9. doi: 10.1016/j.bmcl.2004.09.072, PMID15546729.